

SMARTER GOALS FOR BETTER FUTURE

35th EACD Annual Meeting European Academy of Childhood Disability BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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SMARTER GOALS FOR BETTER FUTURE

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CONTENTS

Welcome Address	iv
Committees	v
Sponsors	vii
Abstracts	viii
Table of Contents	1
Keynote Lectures	21
Oral Communication	27
Poster Presentations	172
Author index	506

WELCOME ADDRESS

Dear Colleagues and Friends!

On behalf of the Scientific and Organizing committee of the 35th European Academy of Childhood Disability (EACD) Annual Meeting, it is a privilege and great pleasure to welcome you to Ljubljana, from May 24th to 27th 2023.

I would like to thank you for giving us the opportunity to host this event. Following the outstanding line of previous EACD annual meetings, we will do our best in offering an excellent opportunity to share experiences, exchange scientific ideas, and foster interactions between all professionals, children and their families.

The motto of this EACD annual meeting is "Smarter Goals for Better Future", with the intent to emphasize the importance of goal setting in all processes of care in the rehabilitation of children and youth.

Further, it is a great pleasure to announce a number of excellent keynotes with prestigious professionals in the field of childhood-onset disability.

Slovenia, your host country, tells its green story. Everything is green no matter which direction you turn – towards the Alpine peaks and extensive forests, the Adriatic Sea, the mysterious Karst and nearby vineyards, and the Pannonian Plain. Ljubljana

Ljubljana, the capital city, is a vibrant city with thousands of years of history. The European Green Capital 2016 has in a short time become a model of livability and eco-sustainability for all medium-sized cities in Europe. Our conference venue is in the city center, which is closed to traffic.

On behalf of the European Academy of Childhood Disability – EACD and University Rehabilitation Institute Republic of Slovenia, we look forward to welcoming you to the 35th EACD Conference!

Yours faithfully,

Asist. prof. Katja Groleger Sršen, MD, PhD

President of the Local Scientific and Organizing Committee

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BAUSCH HEALTH

Motor performance of children with cerebral palsy during the interaction with robot

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Introduction: Different agents, techniques, and recently different types of robots are used in the treatment of children with cerebral palsy. Today, with the development of technology social robots could be used during habilitation of children with cerebral palsy. The aim of this research was to evaluate the motor performance of children with cerebral palsy after interacting with the social assistive robot - Marko (Mobile Anthropomorphic Robot of Cognitive Traits).

Patients and Methods: The research was retrospective, by reviewing videos recorded during the children's sessions with the robot at the Clinic for Children's Rehabilitation in Novi Sad. Eight children with cerebral palsy participated in the research. There were five boys and three girls. The average age of the participants was 9.21 years. Of the eight children with cerebral palsy, four also had mental retardation. We used evaluation according to the grading system described in the article of Fridrin M. and Belkopoyatova M .

Results: In the first session, there is no statistically significant difference in the performance of motor actions between children who have cerebral palsy and mental retardation and children who have cerebral palsy without mental retardation. During the second session success in motor performance in whole group was lower (90.62% vs 81.94%). Children who have mental retardation perform worse motor performance. (74.07% vs 86.57%).

Conclusion: The motivation of children with mental retardation decreased during second session, but the rest of the group still shows satisfactory motivation while practicing with the robot.

Relevance for users and families:

The Introduction of robots into the process of children's rehabilitation can help with motivation during exercise, especially in children without mental retardation. Parents had a positive opinion about the Introduction of the robot during therapy.